

1 BIODATA

- **Name:** Jean-Paul NGBOLUA KOTO-TE-NYIWA
- **Designation:** Full Professor, University of Kinshasa, Congo DR
- **Research field:** Biosciences-Ethnobiology-Biodiversity/Environment
- **H-index:** 31 (Google Scholar); 34 (Researchgate)
- **Nationality:** Congolese (Democratic Republic of the Congo)
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2 EDUCATION

- **Ph.D.** in Molecular Biology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR (2012)
- **M.Sc.** in Molecular Biology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR (2005)
- **B.Sc. Hons.** in Biological Sciences, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR (2002)

3 RESEARCH AND PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCES

- September 2016-July 2021- Rector of the University of Gbado-Lite, Congo DR
- April 09 2018-present: Full Professor, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR.
- May 09, 2012-April 09, 2018: Associate Professor, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR. 09/05/2012 au 09/04/2018
- March 05, 2010 to May 09, 2012: Senior Lecturer, Department of Biology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR.
- November 30, 2004 to March 05, 2010: Junior Lecturer, Department of Biology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR.
- TWAS PhD Research Scientist Fellow (2010), Institut Malgache de Recherches Appliquées, Fondation Albert Ratsimamanga, Antananarivo, Madagascar.
- IFS Doctoral Fellow (2010), Department of Biology, University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, Congo DR.
- Visiting centers: (a) Malagasy Institute of Applied Research (IMRA), Madagascar; (b) Malaria Research and Training Centre, University of Bamako (Mali); (c) Department of Biochemistry, Cell and Molecular Biology, University of Ghana, Accra/Legon (Ghana); (d) Ibadan (Nigeria), Department of Physiology, College of Medicine, University of Ibadan; (e) Cotonou (Bénin), National Academy of Sciences, Arts and Letters; (f) Merck Africa Research Summit (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia); (g) Merck Africa Research Summit (Port-Louis, Mauritius).
- **Winner of MARS Best Young African Researchers Award –Merck Foundation Africa Research Summit - MARS 2021.**

4 SELECTED PUBLICATIONS AND WEB SITES

- *Phytomedicine* 14: 192-195; 2007.
- *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 120: 413-418; 2008.
- *Blood Transfusion* 8: 248-254; 2010.
- *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 144: 39-43; 2012.
- *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine* 3(11): 885-890; 2013.
- *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine* 3(10): 780-784, 2013.
- *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine* 4(3): 169-175; 2014.
- *Pharmaceutical Science and Technology* 2(2): 7-13; 2018.
- *Rwanda Medical Journal* 75 (1): 14-22, 2018.
- *Frontiers in Environmental Microbiology* 4(1): 29-40, 2018.
- *South Asian Research Journal of Natural Products* 2(2): 1-16; 2019.
- *Emergent Life Science Res*, 6(1), 64-75, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.31783/elsr.2020.616475>
- *Chemical Physics Letters*, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2020.137751>
- https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jean_Paul_Ngbolua;
- <http://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=Of8hhVYAAAAJ&hl=fr>